

Chronoamperometry of Cadmium Telluride at Hanging Mercury Drop Electrode

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The electrochemical reduction of semiconductor grade cadmium telluride at the hanging mercury drop electrode has been studied chronoamperometrically in various aqueous supporting electrolytes. Diffusion coefficients for the reduction of Cd(2+) to Cd(0) and Te(4+) to Te(0) are reported. The experimental results are utilised to determine the stoichiometry of cadmium and tellurium present on a semiconductor glass impregnated thin film prepared by vacuum evaporation technique.

THE electrochemical properties of Cd(2+) were studied extensively¹⁻⁵ using different techniques because of its favourable voltammetric characteristics. The reduction mechanism of this metal ion has been studied using the techniques of potential sweep chronoamperometry⁶ and galvanostatic method⁷. Hamelin⁸ studied the reduction behaviour at hanging mercury drop electrode (HMDE) in 0.5 M sodium sulphate solution. It has been estimated using different supporting electrolytes and in presence of several other metals^{6,10}. The electrochemical behaviour of tellurium is very complex because of its different valence states. Polarography and controlled potential coulometry were used by Schwaer and Suchy¹¹ and Lingane and Niedrach^{12,13} to study the electrochemical behaviour of tellurium in different valence states. Because of the use of cadmium telluride in semiconductor technology as also the biological importance of Cd and Te and their toxic effects, the two have been estimated in recent times individually, simultaneously and in presence of several other metals, mostly using electroanalytical techniques such as pulse polarography and stripping analysis¹⁴⁻²⁵. Neutron activation analysis²⁶ and atomic absorption spectrophotometric analysis²⁸ have also been used for the estimation of tellurium. Cyclic voltammetry has been successfully employed by us²⁹ in the determination of these two metals simultaneously. In this communication, we report the attempt to estimate both cadmium and tellurium simultaneously on a glass impregnated thin film using chronoamperometry, besides evaluating the diffusion coefficient values for the reductions of Cd(2+)→Cd(0) and Te(4+)→Te(0).

Experimental

Chronoamperograms were recorded with a Princeton Applied Research Corporation (PARC) model 370 electrochemical module, coupled with Houston instruments X/t Y recorder. A three electrode assembly comprising HMDE as working, isolated

platinum wire as counter and saturated calomel as reference electrodes put into a cup shaped electrolysis cell, is used throughout the studies. Double distilled mercury has been used to fill up HMDE, and was maintained with a constant effective electrochemical area of 0.02695 sq. cm, which was calculated using the chronoamperometric reduction of standard Cd(2+) solution. Purified nitrogen gas was used for deoxygenation and to maintain inert atmosphere in the cell. Philips model 1009 X-ray diffractometer was used for X-ray diffraction measurements and Hind high vacuum model 12A4 coating unit was used to prepare the glass impregnated thin films.

A semiconductor grade sample (99.99% purity) of cadmium telluride supplied by Koch-Light Laboratories, England was used for thin film formation and stock solution preparation. All other chemicals were of AnalaR grade. All supporting electrolytes used namely, 1.0 M hydrochloric acid, 1.0 M potassium chloride, 0.1 M potassium iodide, saturated tartaric acid and 0.1 M potassium iodide saturated with tartaric acid (0.1 M KISTA) were prepared in triple distilled water. 0.1 M KISTA was prepared by dissolving tartaric acid in 0.1 M potassium iodide till saturation limit.

A weighed amount of the sample (CdTe) was dissolved in minimum amount of conc. hydrochloric acid and a few drops of conc. nitric acid. Traces of bromine were added for effective dissolution and any excess was removed by the addition of formic acid. This solution with a few ml triple distilled water was digested on a hot plate at 40-45° for about 15 min. The solution thus obtained was diluted to a required concentration. By using appropriate amounts of solvents, the thin films were also brought into solution and made up with the supporting electrolyte itself.

Delahay³⁰ has discussed the theoretical principles of chronoamperometry, and the technique was extensively used by Jayarama Reddy and Krishnan³¹⁻⁴² in understanding the behaviour of

electrochemical oxidation of several organic species. A potential step corresponding to the diffusion limiting region obtained from cyclic voltammetric results²⁹ was applied to HMDE in all the chronoamperometric experiments for the reduction of both the species. The resulting current-time response is followed by Cottrell relation, which under semi-infinite linear diffusion controlled conditions is given as

$$i_t = \frac{nFAD^{1/2}C}{\pi^{1/2}t^{1/2}} \quad \dots (1)$$

where i_t = instantaneous current in microamperes,

n = number of electrons involved in the overall electrode reaction,

A = area of the electrode in sq. cm,

D = diffusion coefficient in $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$,

C = concentration of electroactive species in mM,

F = Faraday in coulombs,

and t = time in seconds.

A modified form of the above equation⁴⁸ as shown below was used in the evaluation of diffusion coefficient data.

$$D = \left(\frac{(it^{1/2})_0}{54.5 \times 10^8 nAC} \right)^2 \quad \dots (2)$$

where $(it^{1/2})_0$ is the value of $it^{1/2}$ extrapolated to zero time and the constant 54.5×10^8 is the product of F and $\pi^{-1/2}$ in equation (1). All other terms have their usual significance.

Results and Discussion

X-ray diffraction measurements show that the cadmium telluride sample used in the present study has a molecular formula of CdTe, (the experimental lattice parameter value of $a=c=6.48 \text{ \AA}$ compares well with the theoretical value of 6.47 \AA obtained for CdTe by Zachariasen⁴⁴) suggesting the valence state of cadmium to be (2+) and that of tellurium to be (2-). But the presence of Cd(2+) and Te(4+) in the present stock solution was identified by our experimental results²⁹ and typical qualitative

tests. The theoretical explanation being that tellurides can convert themselves to more stable valence states and can be present as tellurous acid in presence of strong oxidising agents such as conc. nitric acid and bromine⁴⁵. The presence of Te(4+) in the test solution is thus justified.

From the cyclic voltammetric results of cadmium telluride reduction²⁹, it is observed that both Cd(2+) and Te(4+) undergo reduction in all the supporting electrolytes employed. Depending upon the pH and viscosity of the supporting electrolyte Cd(2+) reduces within the peak potential range of -0.63 to -0.67 V vs SCE . The Te(4+) undergoes a consecutive reduction to produce Te(2-) via Te(0). An ill defined peak at $\sim -0.55 \text{ V vs SCE}$ is observed for the reduction of Te(4+) \rightarrow Te(0) and a well defined reduction peak due to Te(0) \rightarrow Te(2-) at about -1.12 V (this reduction peak being irreversible varies with concentration, sweep rate and supporting electrolyte) is observed. A peak is also observed at about -1.20 V in some cases due to the reduction of elemental tellurium formed because of a subsequent chemical reaction. Therefore, the current-time curves in chronoamperometry were recorded by stepping the potential from 0.0 V to the corresponding diffusion limited region obtained from cyclic voltammetric data. Typical chronoamperometric curves for the reduction of cadmium telluride in 1.0 M potassium chloride at -0.80 V , and -1.20 V [corresponding to the reductions of Cd(2+) \rightarrow Cd(0) and Te(0) \rightarrow Te(2-)] are shown in Fig. 1. As observed from Fig. 1 in the other supporting electrolytes also, the current decays with time smoothly and reaches a steady state within about 10 sec . Table 1 presents the current-time data obtained in different supporting electrolytes, the potential steps employed and the concentration of the electroactive species used. The data at other concentrations also follow the same pattern. Diffusion coefficients calculated at different concentrations in different supporting electrolytes are presented in Table 2.

The cyclic voltammetric behaviour of cadmium selenide²⁹ and cadmium telluride⁴⁶ reveals that both selenium and tellurium undergo reduction in a similar fashion. The similarities being (i) both Se(4+) and Te(4+) reduce to M(2-) via M(0) (M

Fig. 1. Typical chronoamperometric curves for the reduction of cadmium telluride in 1.0 M potassium chloride. Conc: 2.1020 mM . (a) Potential step: -0.80 V ; (b) Potential step: -1.20 V .

TABLE 1—CHRONOAMPEROMETRIC DATA OF CADMIUM TELLURIDE REDUCTION

Sl. No.	Time sec.	Current μA									
		1.0 M HCl		1.0 M KCl		0.1 M KI		STA ^a		0.1 M KISTA ^b	
1.	0.0	28.0	58.4	32.0	46.8	32.4	99.2	23.2	32.0	24.8	65.2
2.	0.5	11.6	22.0	12.8	20.8	13.6	65.2	8.4	16.4	8.8	34.0
3.	1.0	8.4	16.8	9.2	14.4	10.0	38.4	5.8	13.0	6.4	22.8
4.	1.5	7.0	14.6	7.6	12.8	8.2	26.0	4.8	11.6	5.2	18.4
5.	2.0	6.2	13.6	6.8	12.0	7.2	24.8	4.2	10.6	4.6	15.6
6.	2.5	—	12.8	6.0	—	6.6	18.0	3.8	10.0	—	14.0
7.	3.0	5.2	12.0	5.6	11.2	6.0	16.0	3.4	9.4	4.4	13.2
8.	4.0	4.6	11.0	5.0	10.8	5.2	13.6	3.0	8.8	3.4	11.6
9.	5.0	4.2	10.4	4.4	10.6	4.8	12.4	2.6	8.2	3.2	10.8
10.	6.0	3.8	10.0	4.0	10.4	4.4	11.6	2.4	7.8	3.0	10.2
11.	7.0	3.6	9.6	3.8	10.2	4.2	11.0	2.2	7.6	2.8	9.8
12.	8.0	3.4	9.4	3.6	10.0	3.8	10.6	2.0	7.4	2.8	9.4
13.	9.0	3.2	9.2	3.4	9.8	3.6	10.4	2.0	7.2	2.6	9.2
14.	10.0	3.0	9.2	3.2	9.8	3.6	10.4	1.8	7.0	2.6	9.0
Potential employed in Volt		-0.80	-1.10	-0.80	-1.20	-0.80	-1.30	-0.80	-1.20	-0.80	-1.20
Concentration of electroactive species in mM		2.1020		2.6275		2.6275		3.0028		3.0029	

a : Saturated tartaric acid.
b : 0.1 M potassium iodide saturated with tartaric acid.

TABLE 2—CHRONOAMPEROMETRIC DATA OF CADMIUM TELLURIDE DIFFUSION COEFFICIENT VALUES

Sl. No.	Supporting electrolyte	Conc. mM	Potential step employed [*] / -V Te(0)→Te(2-)	$D \times 10^6 / \text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$	
				Cd(2+)	Te(4+)
1.	1.0 M HCl	0.8085	1.10	2.69	2.04
		1.5014	1.10	2.64	1.72
		2.1020	1.10	2.08	1.76
		2.6275	1.10	1.89	1.08
		3.0912	1.10	1.68	2.21
2.	1.0 M KCl	0.8085	1.20	1.70	0.07
		1.5014	1.20	1.56	0.10
		2.1020	1.20	1.52	0.38
		2.6275	1.20	1.45	0.34
		3.0912	1.20	1.49	0.71
3.	0.1 M KI	0.8085	1.20	2.17	2.18
		1.5014	1.30	1.98	7.15
		2.1020	1.30	1.82	4.19
		2.6275	1.30	1.64	2.88
		3.0912	1.40	1.86	4.89
4.	STA	0.8085	1.10	0.30	0.51
		1.5014	1.20	0.35	1.64
		3.0028	1.20	0.43	0.98
		3.9413	1.30	0.46	0.68
		4.6711	1.30	0.57	0.54
5.	0.1 M KISTA	0.8085	1.10	1.02	5.56
		1.7517	1.20	0.57	1.65
		2.4254	1.20	0.68	1.63
		3.0029	1.20	0.66	1.49
		3.5033	1.20	0.77	1.52

* Potential step employed for Cd(2+)→Cd(0) in all the cases is -0.80 V.

through M(4+)→M(0), which precedes the reduction of Cd(2+)→Cd(0).

In the light of the similarities observed in cyclic voltammetric results, a similar type of reduction behaviour is expected with the chronoamperometric reductions of cadmium selenide and cadmium telluride. In our earlier communication^{4,7} dealing with the chronoamperometric reduction of cadmium selenide it was concluded that only Se(4+)→Se(0) reduction can be studied. In the present case, however, both reductions are observed. The absence of the reductions of Cd(2+)→Cd(0) and Se(0)→Se(2-) in CdSe can be attributed to the following reasons: (i) though Cd(2+)→Cd(0) reduction succeeds the reduction of M(4+)→M(0) in either case, the proximity between the two individual reductions is greater in the case of Te(4+) and Cd(2+) than that in the case of Se(4+) and Cd(2+) and (ii) for a given concentration peak heights observed for the reduction of Se(4+) is found to be greater than that for Te(4+) reduction. It is probable that the electrode is relatively more vitiated by Se(0) than Te(0). Thus though two different potential steps are employed to study the reduction of Cd(2+) and Se(0) individually, similar $it^{1/2}$ values and almost equal $(it^{1/2})_0$ values attributed to Se(4+) were observed in the case of cadmium selenide, whereas in cadmium telluride, both Cd(2+)→Cd(0) and Te(0)→Te(2-) can be considered.

denoting either of the metals), (ii) in either case two types of M(0) are observed one being electrochemically produced and the other being chemically produced and (iii) a reduction peak due to Cd(2+) associated with the two M(4+) ions reduction, is observed only in the second forward scan due to the vitiation of electrode surface by M(0) produced

From the experimental results observed, the $it^{1/2}$ vs t plots are found to be linear and almost horizontal at the first potential step. The number of electrons involved in the electrode process (which are not reported) and the diffusion coefficients evaluated for both the species are found to be lower than the theoretical values (Table 2). Figs. 2 and 3 represent

the variation of $it^{1/2}$ vs t at different concentrations in 1.0 M hydrochloric acid, at -0.80 V and -1.10 V vs SCE as the potential steps employed.

In spite of the adsorption complications noticed, good calibration plots are obtained between concentration and $(it^{1/2})_0$ values, for both the reductions in all the supporting electrolytes. Figs. 4 and 5 represent the calibration plots which are used to deduce the stoichiometric composition of the cadmium telluride thin films of different thicknesses prepared on a glass substrate by vacuum evaporation technique (some of the calibration plots are not shown in the figures as they are merging with the presented ones). The $(it^{1/2})_0$ values obtained for the thin film solution at the two different potential steps are employed to know the concentrations of the ingredients and in turn the stoichiometry. Satisfactory agreement is observed between the average experimental value (average for five determinations) and that of the theoretical value for stoichiometry in all the supporting electrolytes. (theoretical: 46.833% Cd and 53.166% Te : experimental : 45.917% Cd and 54.085% Te).

Diffusion coefficient data for both Cd(2+) and Te(4+) are presented in Table 2. Though the potential step employed in the case of tellurium correspond to the diffusion limited region for the reduction of Te(0)→Te(2-), the Te(0) formation at the electrode is governed by the diffusion of Te(4+). Therefore these diffusion coefficient values can be

Fig. 2. t vs $it^{1/2}$ plots for cadmium telluride reduction in 1.0 M hydrochloric acid. Potential step : -0.80 V. Conc : (a) 0.8085 mM ; (b) 1.5014 mM ; (c) 2.100 mM ; (d) 2.6275 mM ; (e) 3.0912 mM.

Fig. 3. t vs $it^{1/2}$ plots for cadmium telluride reduction in 1.0 M hydrochloric acid. Potential step : -1.10 V. Conc : (a) 0.8085 mM ; (b) 1.5014 mM ; (c) 2.1020 mM ; (d) 2.6275 mM.

Fig. 4. Calibration plots of cadmium telluride reduction at -0.80 V in (a) 0.1 M potassium iodide, (b) 1.0 M potassium chloride, (c) 0.1 M potassium iodide saturated with tartaric acid.

Fig. 5. Calibration plots of cadmium telluride reduction at second potential step.

(a) 0.1 M potassium iodide, (b) 1.0 M hydrochloric acid, (c) 0.1 M potassium iodide saturated with tartaric acid, (d) 1.0 M potassium chloride.

attributed to $\text{Te}(4+)$. In all the supporting electrolytes the diffusion coefficient values obtained are on the lower side of the theoretical values^{48,49} [$\text{Cd}(2+)$: $7.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in 0.1 M KCl and $\text{Te}(4+)$: $8.3 \times 10^{-6} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ in 0.1 M ammonium chloride and 0.3 M ammonium hydroxide buffer] due to adsorption complications. In the case of STA and 0.1 M KISTA, the values are relatively lower than in the other supporting electrolytes, probably because of high viscosity of the medium.

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